

Nutrition of Children Playing Table Tennis in Sports Clubs of General Education Schools I

Xayitov Javoxir Baxodirovchi, Raxmatov Sardor Salim o'g'li

Tashkent medicine academy

Abstract: of my organization carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins and minerals ensure balance athletes for all food substances important have Spotter children organism for, nutritional of substances each one's ratio food to the type of sport played by substances looking quantity difference does Nutrition quality future of champions to energy and their training sessions efficiency directly effect does With regular sports engaged in competitions during always physical to cry and psychological stress from the head forgiving children more attention and caring demand does.

Keywords: table tennis, sports clubs, food substances.

The purpose of the study is to study the nutrition of children who play table tennis in sports clubs of general education schools.

The tasks of the research: to study the level and system of diseases of children and teenage athletes who regularly play table tennis, to study health and preventive measures;

the hygienic evaluation of actual nutrition of children and teenage athletes who regularly play table tennis, optimization of organization of actual nutrition;

As an object of research , children and teenagers who play table tennis from 12 to 16 years old (200 children and teenagers: 136 boys, 64 girls)

Subject of research: assessment of the disease level and system of children and adolescents who regularly play table tennis; hygienic evaluation of actual food organization and quality; distribution of new food for children and teenagers who play table tennis.

Methods of research: a number of methods related to the assigned tasks were used in the course of scientific research: questionnaire, analytical and statistical methods.

The scientific novelty of the research is as follows:

Peculiar aspects of the nutritional status of children and adolescent athletes playing table tennis were studied according to indicators: the health status of children was evaluated by dividing into the main class and nosological form of the disease, nutritional system and energy supply. ;

It is necessary to control the consumption of clean water with enough nutrients for the body, because children are very active on their own and athletes move even more . Sweating causes the body to lose a lot of fluid, which can lead to dehydration, so your child needs to drink more water , the inability to resist unpleasant environmental factors , and the deterioration of mental and physical performance.

of my organization carbohydrates , proteins , fats , vitamins and minerals ensure balance athletes for all food substances important important have Spotter children organism for , nutritional of substances each one's ratio food to the type of sport played by substances looking quantity difference does Nutrition quality future of champions to energy and their training sessions efficiency directly effect does With regular sports engaged in competitions during always physical to cry and psychological stress from the head forgiving children more attention and caring demand does Children and teenage athletes organism for proteins and carbohydrates, as well as vitamins and minerals from food level provision need

A healthy child is the main problem in the near and long future of any country, all opportunities (economic, creative), all social and economic development prospects, high standard of living, science and culture - all these are related to children's health, physical and mental work. is achieved as a result of competence

During exercise, the metabolism accelerates and nutrients are consumed more quickly. In children, this process occurs 1.5-2 times more intensively than in adults, so they need to get more calories. The norm for boys aged 6-12 is 2000-2600 kcal per day, for girls - 1800-2200 kcal. In this case, the total caloric content of the daily diet may be 10% higher than the energy expenditure.

Choosing a sufficient type of nutrition (products, nutrients and their combinations) to ensure different directions of the diet (protein, carbohydrate, protein-carbohydrate) in the exercises aimed at preparing athletes separately for competitions, depending on the specific pedagogical task ; distributing the ration throughout the day according to the type and order of training and competitions. The nutrition of children involved in sports should not only be related to the need to achieve effective training and high sports performance, but should also meet the need for nutrients and energy that support the child's growth and development. Adequate water-salt regime during active physical exertion prevents losses due to sweating and increased fluid flow, microelements, primarily sodium and potassium, maintain the functional state of the heart-blood, nervous-muscle system. It is important to take into account the type of sport that a young athlete is engaged in, the duration of training, when organizing the order of drinking water. Sports drinks are recommended for those who practice long-term sports. It is considered necessary for athletes to drink fluids before, during and after training.

In conclusion, the nutrition of children involved in sports should satisfy the need for nutrients and energy, which support the child's continuous growth and development, not only for the effective training process and high sports performance. Rational organization of meals helps in the process of strengthening health, increasing sports ability, recovery and adaptation to physical loads.

REFERENCES

1. Гигиенические требования к организации питания учащихся спортивных школ Республики Узбекистан СанПин РУз №0333-16 Ташкент, 2016 – С. 3-30.
2. Гигиенические требования к построению рационального питания и методы определения потребности в энергии и пищевых веществах. // Учебное пособие к практическим занятиям по гигиене питания Под редакцией проф. Г.И.Шайховой. Ташкент, 2014. – С.40-48.
3. Гишак Т.В., Горчакова Н.А., Гунина Л.М. и др. Спортивная фармакология и диетология // под ред. С. А. Олейника, Л. М. Луниной. - Москва: ООО «ИД Вильямс», 2008. - 256 с.
4. Гольберг Н.Д., Дондуковская Р.Р. Питание юных спортсменов. // - М., изд. Советский спорт. – 2012. – 236с.
5. Григоренко С.П. Совершенствование технологии производства рыборастворительных колбасных изделий для питания юношей и девушек, занятых умственным трудом. // Автореф. дис. к.т.н. Краснодар: КубГТУ, 2005. - 24 с.
6. Гринченко В.С., Мазуренко Е.А. Технологии специализированных продуктов питания для спортсменов. // Краснодар: Дом-Юг, 2015. - 176 с.
7. Гринченко В.С., Касьянов Г.И. Новый подход к разработке продуктов питания для шахматистов. //Научные труды Куб.ГТУ-№ 12.- 2016.- С.141-155.
8. Детская спортивная медицина. Под ред. С. Б. Тихвинского, С. В. Хрущева. М. -1991. - 560 с.
9. Дондуковская Р.Р. Гигиеническая оценка статуса питания юных спортсменов и пути его коррекции // Автореферат дисс. на канд.мед.наук. –М.2005. С.3-5.

10. Abdurakhimov, B. A., Khaitov, J. B., Safarov, K. K., & Ulmasov, J. M. (2023). A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO MANAGING THE HEALTH AND RISK FACTORS OF THEIR WORKERS. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(2), 209-213.
11. Khaitov, J. B. (2022). Hygienic assessment of boiled sausages and sausages produced by «Rozmetov»(Uzbekistan). *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 1382-1384.
12. Шайхова, Г. И., & Хайитов, Ж. Б. (2020). Гигиеническая оценка фактического питания детей-спортсменов, занимающихся шахматами. *Медицинские новости*, (5 (308)), 75-78.